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Technologies and collaboration for sustained Arctic Ocean Observing Systems (A00S)

D6: Data management, distribution, and cost estimation

Figure 3: Outline of the functional components.

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Executive summary

Deliverable D6 presents the data management framework, distribution approach, and cost-estimation principles needed for the future Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS). Developed in Work Package 4, it draws on earlier AOOS deliverables and results from a Big Data workshop. The report explains how AOOS should manage, process, share, and sustain Arctic observational data for research, operational services, and decision-making. Because the observing system design is still evolving, the report emphasises principles and high-level architecture rather than prescribing specific technologies.

User needs identified in D4 include better coordination and standardisation of in situ observations—especially biological measurements—along with real-time and delayed-mode access for forecasting and operational use. Data must follow open licensing practices such as NLOD or CC-BY-4.0, use persistent identifiers, meet CoreTrustSeal requirements, follow FAIR principles, and where relevant be delivered to the Copernicus Marine Service. Combined with the technical specifications in D5, these needs call for a system capable of handling diverse sensors, variable sampling rates, and multiple communication modes (e.g., physical retrieval, radio, satellite, mobile networks, and internet-based transfer). Dissemination must also support the WMO GTS/WIS2.0 framework.

The Big Data workshop confirmed the need for a federated approach, allowing harmonised access to distributed datasets regardless of where they are stored. Participants stressed the importance of open standards such as OGC and STAC, together with clear APIs that ensure platform interoperability. They also highlighted the value of data services that avoid unnecessary large-scale data transfers, the benefits of open-source solutions to reduce vendor dependence, and the need for secure handling of sensitive or restricted information.

FAIR-aligned data practices are central to D6, especially the need for machine-actionable interoperability. The report recommends standardised, semantically rich formats such as CF-compliant NetCDF and ODV ASCII, supported by structured metadata frameworks including OAI-PMH, DCAT, and schema.org. Ensuring clear provenance, quality information, and controlled vocabularies is essential for reusable data.

A broad technology landscape underpins the future system. Communication options include cabled observatories like LoVe Ocean, satellite systems such as Iridium and Starlink, mobile networks, and future submarine cables like Polar Connect and Far North Fiber. Emerging techniques such as Distributed Acoustic Sensing and State of Polarization sensing may provide new communication options under ice. Storage must be scalable and interoperable, ranging from high-performance file systems and object stores to hybrid cloud systems and national research storage such as NIRD Data Peak and Data Lake. Processing will use a mix of HPC systems, virtual machines, microservices, and cloud-based workflows, supported by Sigma2, institutional platforms, and European HPC resources.

The architecture proposed in D6 reflects AOOS's evolving and heterogeneous environment. It must be modular, service-oriented, and cost-efficient; extensible to new sensors and data types; flexible to technological change; and interoperable with frameworks such as Copernicus, EMODnet, EOSC, and BarentsWatch. Security, reliability, and data-integrity safeguards are essential, especially given the geopolitical context in the Arctic. The system must also remain usable for both expert and non-expert members of the community.

The report recommends a rental-model approach rather than giving specific cost figures, using units like Tebibytes per year, CPU/GPU-hours, and GB/s of bandwidth. National research infrastructures usually offer cheap bandwidth but more costly storage, while commercial clouds reverse this pattern. Large, long-term systems tend to benefit from hybrid or on-premise solutions, whereas smaller or occasional activities may be cheaper to outsource. Long-term costs are uncertain due to geopolitics, data-sensitivity issues, and changing regulations.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS) is a planning and collaboration project for strengthening the Norwegian role in Arctic Observing.

Within the AOOS project, Work Package 4 have leveraged data processing, storage, and distribution technologies for big data and ocean data, using the expertise of the consortium augmented with input from invited experts to workshops and meetings. Partners have engaged with Norwegian companies in the big data industry, established marine data infrastructures nationally and internationally and major international data initiatives and ecosystems such as the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO), SAON/IASC Arctic Data Committee, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and Destination Earth and Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE). This has enabled identification of important technological advances in data digitalization for environmental data, and evaluation of how to utilise these.

The purpose of this report is to outline the data management and distribution system according to identified user requirements for data and services on data and estimate costs for implementation. Contents of the report depends on decisions on the design of the observing system and final priorities for implementation.

1.2 Applicable documents

Work package 4 is based on input provided by work packages 2 and 3, “Concept of ocean observing networks for societal needs” and “Technological specification of the sub-systems of the AOOS”, respectively. These 2 work packages are providing the deliverables

- D4 - User needs of in situ ocean observations in the Arctic (WP 2)
- D5 - Specification and cost estimates of the components of the AOOS (WP 3)

which are used as input for the work undertaken in WP 4.

These deliverables are in turn based on work carried out in WP1 “Arctic Policies, Roadmaps and strategies for ocean observations”. WP1 are providing the deliverables

- D1 - Guidelines and requirements for AOOS
- D2 - Report from workshops in Tromsø and Stavanger in 2024

which provides high-level requirements and identifies some of the ocean observing technologies and data management systems that can form building blocks for the AOOS.

In addition to the deliverables specified above, a workshop on big data storage and distribution was arranged by the project (WP4) autumn 2024 in Bergen. The results of this workshop is summarised in a report (Hamre et al., 2026).

1.3 Organisation of the report

The report is structured into a data management and requirements section which describes practises of distributed data management and identified requirements within the project. This is followed by a section on technologies that are used today or emerging and considered applicable to the project additionally extended by an analysis of technologies in relation to requirements. And then a high level architecture serving as foundation for a coarse cost estimate to achieve this. Major findings are then summarised.

2 Data management and requirements

2.1 Data management in practise

2.1.1 Best practises for data management

Best practises for data management are addressed by the FAIR Guiding Principles (Wilkinson et al, 2016). FAIR in this context covers Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reuseable data and services. These principles addresses relevant issues that has to be covered and the intention is have machine actionable data and web services. In daily practise many use the phrase FAIR data when they mean Findable and Accessible data. The challenge when creating fully machine actionable data lies in the Interoperable part. The FAIR guiding principles are developed around a concept of a dataset. The following definition of a dataset is taken from the Polar Semantics Working Group, a joint effort between SAON and IARPC. *A dataset is a collection of data items that has a reference to a geographical area and a designated start and end time. It can contain observations (in situ, remote sensing, local and traditional knowledge in any form), derived quantities (by processing/transformation of observations, numerical simulations etc.) describing features of the surrounding environment in the past, presence or future. Data values can be located at a single point, along a line or transect, in regular or irregular grid etc. and be captured/observed or estimated at one or more altitudes/depths. A dataset can be stored on paper (or other physical media like wood, woven material), in files (one or more) or database. Data without a context does not qualify as a dataset, meaning that additional metadata is required to properly describe and allow interpretation of data to qualify as a dataset.* In the context of AOOS, all datasets have a digital representation and are to a wide extent provided by digital sensors. Each dataset has to be described by discovery metadata (similar to index cards in a library) that are made available through searchable catalogues with human and machine interfaces. Key aspects of discovery metadata are utilisation of persistent identifiers, utilisation of standards for describing datasets, and utilisation of controlled vocabularies and terminologies with agreed definitions. Accessible implies that data are made available using standard protocols. In the simplest form this is e.g. direct download through HTTP, but it could imply authentication/authorisation. Interoperable is key for machine actionable data. This directly relates to application of agreed standardised data formats that both have well defined structures and semantic annotations that clearly defines the content of data, including how missing values are encoded, standardised variable definitions, clear definitions of auxiliary coordinates of the data (e.g. spatiotemporal) etc. Examples of fully Interoperable file formats are e.g. NetCDF following the Climate and Forecast (CF) Conventions¹. NetCDF or HDF in itself are not FAIR compliant, but need

¹ <https://cfconventions.org/>
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an agreed structure that properly describes the data content. The same applies to formats like JSON, Parquet, Zarr etc. These formats can be made FAIR compliant though by application of e.g. CF conventions.

2.1.2 Distributed data management

Within distributed data management data repositories collaborate and exchange information about their data holdings using standardised information models and web services. Most data repositories are only exposing their data holdings, others both expose and harvest information and finally there are some that only act as aggregators. For aggregators (both mixed and strict) there are usually 2 main approaches. The most common approach is to harvest information about the datasets (discovery metadata) but let users access data directly from the authoritative data repository. Examples of this approach include national data repositories like NMDC, NorDataNet and SIOS. The other approach is that the full dataset is downloaded and republished within the context of the aggregating data repository. Examples of this are e.g. EMODNet and Copernicus Marine Service In Situ TAC. While this approach can ensure harmonised data documentation, it is of the greatest importance that full provenance is captured and provided to potential data consumers and that the original persistent identifiers are kept throughout the value chain. If not, the consequence is, as often experienced today, it looks like there is much data available in a certain region, but in practise it is merely duplicates of the same dataset. On the other hand a fully distributed system, potentially relying on caching only for real time applications circumvent some political challenges on visibility of data providers and data repositories supporting the first mile of data management. Further to this there is a clear identification and commitment of the authoritative source of the information. The distributed approach also provides a foundation to establish embedded resilience. In this latter context it is important that connected data repositories comply with FAIR and TRUST.

2.1.3 Science for service to society value chains

A major difference between research and operational data management is the focus on services on top of data. This is seldom used in the traditional approach of research data repositories. Normally data are treated as blob of information and the consumers approach is to download everything. In a world of ever increasing data volumes this is not sustainable nor cost efficient. The two main approaches to circumvent this have been: server side data reduction offered by the data repositories (services on top of data), and integration of data into processing platforms (to be discussed next).

But the difference between research and operational data management is becoming blurred recent years. One major reason is that data produced by researchers more and more are used for multiple purposes in society. There are many reasons for this, one is that funders want research to have impact on society but there is also the aspect of maximising the return of investment in research. In remote areas like the Arctic research is often the main source of information that can be used also for management questions. In order to improve the impact of research activities careful thinking on how data are published and whether value adding through post processing (e.g. aggregation of multiple sources or generation of indicators) along with web services on top of the data should be considered. This is already done in many contexts, a good example is the WMO Global Cryosphere Watch. The science for service approach calls for value chain thinking. How can we with the smallest possible cost come from data to a product suitable for decision support. In this context, again provenance or

traceability of the end product back to the input data is critical. Actual decisions are external to the system here, the focus is decision support.

2.1.4 Data access services versus data analytics platform

In Europe over the last years a number of data analytics platforms have been developed (e.g. Sigma2, WekEo, CDSE, EOOSC). The idea is to bring the data consumer to the data and do processing close to the data. The challenge is that these platforms do not necessarily contain all the data a consumer may want to use for the use case explored. These platforms often also have vague business models that are hard to navigate for consumers and they are also often more expensive than self hosted solutions. The latter on the other hand usually require that users have sufficient capacity to host their own hardware. Thus the uptake of solutions like this often depends on the size of the consumer. Adding to this, Norway has a national e-infrastructure that is better than most other countries in Europe making server side data reduction services relevant for many users. Experience from the National Ground Segment for Satellite Data has shown that users normally only use a fraction of the available data in a large dataset (e.g. 15-25% of the full dataset). It clearly doesn't make sense to move the full dataset around in a situation like this. When moving services into a platform, the most vulnerable issue is how to move on to another platform if needed or costs increase. Thus it is likely that a solution would require both web services on top of data and platforms where users without their own infrastructure could process data.

2.1.5 Technological, vendor and business lock in

As indicated in the previous section, business models of platforms or cloud services are often difficult to understand, in particular looking into the future. What is cost efficient and makes sense today is not necessarily the same in 5-10 years. Many large actors has made mistakes on this (e.g. NASA, 2013). When entering into a specific solution, whether this is software or infrastructure, mapping alternatives and developing an exist strategy is important. Unfortunately this is often complicated. For infrastructure, storage is normally rather cheap while bandwidth is expensive. This makes it difficult and expensive to move large volumes of data to a new solution. For software there are commercial solutions that relies on license costs. These solutions are often opaque and lacks the transparency on e.g. processing steps needed to create trust in a product.

2.2 Requirements revisited

2.2.1 User needs of in situ ocean observations in the Arctic

Deliverable D4 of AOOS (Sandven et al., 2025) is generated by Work Package 2. The nature of this deliverable changed from a conceptual design to a user requirements report. The requirements are described in terms of which parameters to measure, and characteristics of the measurements e.g., point measurements, profiles/integrated, measurement cycle, sampling rate, and delivery mode.

For the first it is noted that there is no systematic monitoring of biological parameters in the central Arctic Ocean. In order to address this, better coordination of cruises are requested along with development of standardised observing protocols and a set of standard stations.

For the second, also improved coordination of activities are requested along with standardised data collection and dissemination, supporting real time data is required. Data should be delivered to Copernicus Marine Service.

More specific requirements on data management are related to:

- REQ. 1 Clear identification of data constraints through active use of licenses
- REQ. 2 The recommended license is NLOD or CC-BY-4.0².
- REQ. 3 If NLOD/CC-BY-4.0 is not suitable, the Creative Commons licenses should be used.
- REQ. 4 Active utilisation of persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI).
- REQ. 5 Access to real and near real time data is critical for operational forecasting and decision making.
- REQ. 6 Relevant data are conveyed to Copernicus Marine data Store.
- REQ. 7 Delayed mode data are made available in a timely manner.
- REQ. 8 The FAIR guiding principles are actively used.
- REQ. 9 Data repositories used should be CoreTrustSeal certified.
- REQ. 10 Standardised data formats are used, but the user can request transformations to other formats.
- REQ. 11 Standardised access methods to data are used.

2.2.2 Specification and cost estimates of the components of the AOOS

Deliverable D5 of AOOS (Sandven et al., 2025) outlines cost estimates for the components identified in AOOS. This provides an overview of the types of observations collected by different platforms and sensors which poses requirements on volumes and services needed. This affects the data management services and accompanied costs.

Requirements identified are listed below:

- REQ. 12 Platform communication by direct physical download
- REQ. 13 Platform communication by radio communication
- REQ. 14 Platform communication by satellites (e.g., StarlinkPlatform, Iridium)
- REQ. 15 Dissemination through WMO GTS/WIS2.0 MQTT
- REQ. 16 Platform communication through mobile network (4G/5G)
- REQ. 17 Platform communication by direct internet connection

2.2.3 Workshop on big data and distribution

The workshop on big data and distribution were organised according to the following themes:

²These are compatible.
Date: 2 February 2026

1. Scalability of technologies and frameworks (capabilities and challenges)
2. Information models for complex and heterogeneous data
3. Sustainability of technologies and their implementation (climate footprint)
4. Cost models and funding regime for Big Data storage and computing facilities

Participants were free to raise any issue conceived important to achieve a scalable, cost efficient and robust solution for an Arctic Ocean data system. For details, the reader is referred to the workshop report, but the following aspects were found important:

- REQ. 18 Federation approaches are preferred over monolithic approaches.
- REQ. 19 Interoperability is achieved based on well-defined APIs that follow commonly used standards (e.g. OGC, STAC) and good practices.
- REQ. 20 Harmonised data access enables users to access data independently of its location and underlying protocol.
- REQ. 21 Services around data help avoiding massive data transfers.
- REQ. 22 Support “Bringing-users-to-the-data” paradigm & Processing capabilities & services next to federated data holdings.
- REQ. 23 Open source software is preferred.
- REQ. 24 Commonly used technologies in order to avoid vendor lock-in.
- REQ. 25 Offering various near-data processing services to cater for different user needs (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, FaaS).
- REQ. 26 Interoperability is necessary not only on data and also at platform level.
- REQ. 27 Sensitive data exist and the system has to be able to handle this.
- REQ. 28 Stakeholder communities are diverse and the approach has to address that.
- REQ. 29 At the European level a legislation framework is existing.

3 Technologies

3.1 Information flow

Figure 1 shows the information flow from sensors through various communication subsystems to a designated data repository for the observations collected. Data from sensors are then processed and quality controlled, and the quality

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controlled data are stored in the repository. From the data repository, the data consumers can search for and access data of interest. The data repository may also provide transformation and advanced data access services that enables direct integration of data into decision support systems.

Figure 1: Simple illustration of information flow in the AOOS context.

3.2 Data documentation

Technologies used by partners and consulted external parties for data documentation and formatting in the AOOS project emphasize interoperability, standardization, and openness. Key approaches include use of the FAIR guiding principles, persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs), and open licenses such as CC-BY-4.0. Data formats are standardized where possible using NetCDF (CF-compliant) and ODV ASCII, while metadata is structured via OAI-PMH, schema.org, and DCAT. Systems like METSIS (used in e.g. ADC, NBS, SIOS, NorDataNet), NPDC, and NMDC employ REST APIs, OGC services, and PostgreSQL databases to manage structured and unstructured data. These infrastructures support automated quality control, real-time and delayed-mode data delivery, and transformation services to meet diverse user needs.

3.3 Communication

Communication and transmission technologies used by AOOS partners and consulted external parties are designed to support robust, scalable, and near real-time data delivery from Arctic observing platforms. These include cabled observatories like LoVe Ocean, which use hybrid AC power and fiber-optic cables for high-bandwidth data transmission, and mobile and satellite-based systems (e.g. Iridium, Starlink) for remote buoy/station communication. Advanced techniques like Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarization (SoP) sensing are explored for one-way subsea communication. Data flows are managed through RESTful APIs (e.g. OPeNDAP), OGC services, and cloud infrastructures, enabling automated ingestion, quality control, and secure distribution across national and international platforms.

It is likely to see new communication providers and services emerge in the Arctic, driven by the demand for more diversity and more bandwidth. This will include submarine cable systems (i.e. Polar Connect, Far North Fiber) that may be equipped with SMART functionality. When these systems will be deployed is still unclear, as the investments will require funding exceeding EUR 1bn. Also, satellite system developers (e.g. Space Norway) contemplate investment in new satellite systems covering the main parts of the Arctic. Again, these investments will require significant demand from the commercial market players, the scientific community and governmental bodies.

3.4 Storage

Technologies used by partners and consulted external parties for data storage and distribution emphasize scalability, interoperability, and sustainability. The recommendation is to leverage federated data infrastructures over monolithic systems, enabling harmonized access across distributed repositories. Storage solutions range from local to hosted solutions through private, hybrid and public cloud approaches, with File Storage (e.g. Lustre which is particularly suited for parallel access as demanded by large datasets), object storage systems (e.g., S3) to pure cloud-based platforms like Azure, Google and Amazon and OVHCloud. On the service side, the Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data ([NIRD](#)), operated by Sigma2 has storage organised in 2 different solutions for different purposes, NIRD Data Peak (DP) and NIRD Data Lake (DL). NIRD DP is connected to High Performance Computers operated by Sigma2. The data system architectures also integrate data lakes, data cubes, and trusted research environments to handle sensitive data securely.

3.5 Processing

AOOS partners and consulted external parties employ a range of processing and analysis technologies to support scalable, automated, and high-quality data workflows. Tools like SeisMon and SeisMonPy are used for seismic data analysis, integrating libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, and ObsPy for advanced signal processing. Machine learning models enhance automatic detection, classification, and system health monitoring. For oceanographic data, platforms like the Copernicus Marine Service use automated quality control and NetCDF formatting for both near real-time and delayed-mode data.

Processing environments can be built on premise, bought commercially (e.g. Azure, Google, Amazon, OVHCloud etc) or through national services for research, like Sigma2. Sigma2 has various HPC systems and includes access to resources in EUROHPC. Sigma2 has also processing capacity allocated in the NIRD Service Platform. In the Sigma2 services processing can be done close to data both in HPC and microservices environments. A similar setup is available at MET, this setup is used both for operations and research, with the former having priority. The solutions range from “bare bone”, HPC, Virtual Machines and microservices through e.g. Kubernetes. Processing capacity can be combined with the strong national e-infrastructure in Norway where bandwidth allows integration of processing and storage across physical locations, as implemented in the Norwegian Ground Segment for Satellite data.

Systems such as the MET processing environment and NIRD Service Platform support distributed data processing, visualization, and integration through both HPC, Virtual Machine and cloud-native architectures and microservices. These technologies enable efficient transformation, harmonization, and analysis of heterogeneous datasets across Arctic observation systems. A combination of approaches is required to support processing of the data, including HPC, virtual machines and various container based approaches like K8S. Software and programming languages used for processing and visualisation is heterogeneous, but a tendency towards Python based solutions is observed. This calls for a decentralised hybrid (combination of multiple approaches) opportunistic (use appropriate systems that are available) approach on processing. This can be done relying on the high capacity national broadband.

4 Analysis

4.1 Robustness and scalability

Robustness and scalability are essential to a system like AOOS. Single point of failures needs to be addressed, for some operational use it is expected that duplicate processing and redundant communication channels are needed. There is however a cost/benefit trade off to be made when it comes to redundancy. A more thorough analysis of the impact of various observing systems on operational use cases, in particular those related to various emergency services (e.g. Search and Rescue, oil drift), is needed.

The design of AOOS must address upscaling the system with more platforms and sensors . Such up-scaling would require that the communication, processing and storage solutions allow addition of more sensors and platforms without fully redesigning the architecture. In particular should additional storage and processing capacity be possible at a marginal cost principle. Marginal cost implies that basic investments allows future growth without the need to redo all basic investments when additional capacity is needed. This is the rental model approach that is used in research funding through e.g. national and European funding and also in the commercial cloud providers. This approach is also valid for communication although there are certain limitations on upscaling in this context.

Access to diverse communication platforms (e.g. submarine fiber optic cables and satellite systems), will increase robustness and available bandwidth for current and future AOOS requirements. If, or when, these platforms and communication services will be available, in contingent to demand from commercial market players, the scientific community and governmental agencies and institutions.

4.2 Geopolitics

The geopolitical situation in the Arctic has changed due to the war in Ukraine and tensions in the western world. An expected impact of this is that the ability to constrain access to certain (or all) data is necessary. Although the design is aiming for free and open access to data, the current geopolitical situation indicates that secure communication, data storage and access, is a necessary requirement in the design even for data that aren't sensitive in nature. This implies that ensuring security and integrity throughout the value chains are essential.

4.3 Relevant national and international frameworks

Data exchange has evolved much in recent years. In particular since 2000 frameworks for exchange of climate and environmental data has emerged, at national, regional European and global scales. At the national scale AOOS data management should relate to research infrastructures like Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC) and NorDataNet, but also to management oriented frameworks like BarentsWatch. There are also ideas of establishing a national data space for climate and environmental data which would be relevant in this context if realised. At the European level Copernicus, SeaDataNet and EMODNet are relevant frameworks, but also integration with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) activities as well as Destination Earth and linked activities. Ideally linkages to these frameworks are done in collaboration with the relevant national e-infrastructures.

4.4 Platform communication

Utilizing communication services from a potential future submarine cable system, will require development of new interfaces between observatories and cable systems. It is important to have an ongoing dialogue with the cable developers to assure design principles for the interfaces is met by the cable provider.

Likewise for satellite systems, the interface between an observatory and a satellite system will be an integral part of the satellite terminal connected to the observatory, and should be followed up in a next phase of AOOS.

4.5 Data dissemination

Data dissemination is closely linked with the data exchange frameworks that exist or are planned. Key technologies include, but is not limited to, RESTful API's (e.g. OPeNDAP), OGC Standards, STAC and schema.org for discovery metadata and data access. For a system to become fully functional, the number of interfaces has to be limited to reduce the costs for data providers and consumers on connecting to the data. Agreement on technologies as well as governance in such a system is what is now emerging in the European landscape through the concept of data spaces. Data spaces can be connected to data lake adapters where data are brought close to the processing capacity needed for a specific use case. The processing capacity will differ according to the use case and what is suitable for research is not necessarily suitable for operational purposes and vice versa.

4.6 Design principles

Provided the requirements listed above, the heterogeneous usage community and use cases the following design principles are identified:

I. Modular

A. A modular approach is needed where software components serving specific functionality can be exchanged without changing the whole system.

B.

II. Service oriented

A. Service oriented implies that functionality is implemented as web services that communicate using standardized interfaces. Functional modules are linked using standard communication protocols.

III. Cost efficient

A. The system must be cost efficient to develop, implement and maintain over time ensuring a sustainable system.

IV. Extensible

A. The system must be extensible in the sense that new nodes (data, processing centres) hosted by existing or new partners and potentially serving new data and products must be supported.

V. Flexible

- A. Flexible in the sense of ability to adapt to a rapidly changing world. This implies that data managers etc, shall be able to run and adapt many features (e.g., views on data) of the system without waiting for dedicated system developers.

VI. Interoperable

- A. The system should be able to interact with relevant national and international data management systems.

VII. Reliable

- A. The system must be reliable and stable during operation.

VIII. Secure

- A. The system must ensure access to datasets and processing services is in line with the regulations given by their owners and providers.

IX. Integrity ensured

- A. The system must ensure integrity of the data handled and document this for the users of the system. Data cannot be altered anywhere in the information flow from sensor to consumer.

X. Open data space

- A. Serving an open data space (data types of the future is not known today) and a multitude of interfaces to metadata and data. This implies a tiered approach where user-specific systems (e.g., requiring extremely high throughput or many users) can be built on standardized data management practices. This overlaps with the flexibility principle.

XI. Useable

- A. The system should be intuitive to use for end users as well as for system operators. Support of both machine and human interfaces to metadata, data and web services.

5 Architecture

5.1 Basics of RM-ODP

The Reference Model of Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP) is a framework for designing information systems. It is described in detail in (RM-ODP, 2025) but a brief overview is provided below. The approach covered here is not a full design of the system but a high level perspective on the system to be implemented. RM-ODP relies on viewpoint perspectives of a system. These viewpoints are:

- i. Enterprise viewpoint which is concerned with the purpose, scope and policies governing the activities of the specified system within the organization of which it is a part;
- ii. Information viewpoint which is concerned with the kinds of information handled by the system and constraints on the use and interpretation of that information;

- iii. Computational viewpoint which is concerned with the functional decomposition of the system into a set of objects that interact at interfaces - enabling system distribution;
- iv. Engineering viewpoint which is concerned with the infrastructure required to support system distribution;
- v. Technology viewpoint, which is concerned with the choice of technology to support system distribution.

The RM-ODP framework is widely used to describe Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) architectures. The viewpoints are often illustrated by

Figure 2.

Figure 2: Viewpoints perspective on system design by RM-ODP (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RM-ODP#/media/File:RM-ODP_viewpoints.jpg).

5.2 Enterprise viewpoint

The Enterprise Viewpoint of the Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS) defines the purpose, scope, and governing policies of the data system within the broader organizational and societal context. AOOS is a strategic initiative led by Norwegian institutions to establish a sustained, interoperable,

and scalable Arctic Ocean observing infrastructure. Its primary objectives are to support climate science, marine forecasting, environmental monitoring, and decision-making through long-term, high-quality ocean data collection and distribution.

This viewpoint addresses the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders—including research institutions, governmental bodies, and international partners—and outlines the policies guiding data ownership, licensing (e.g., NLOD, CC-BY-4.0), and FAIR principles. It emphasizes coordination across national and international infrastructures, integration with initiatives like Copernicus, EOSC, and WMO, and alignment with legal frameworks such as the EU Data Act and AI Act.

The AOOS enterprise architecture must support both scientific and operational use cases, and balance open access with secure handling of sensitive data. The architecture promotes federation over centralization, enable distributed data management and harmonized access across different platforms. The AOOS data management system will be designed to be resilient, cost-efficient, and adaptable to evolving user needs and geopolitical conditions.

5.3 Information viewpoint

The Information Viewpoint of the AOOS data system describes the types of information managed by the system, the structure and semantics of that information, and the constraints on its use and interpretation. AOOS handles heterogeneous environmental data collected from a wide range of Arctic observing platforms, including fixed, mobile, and cabled systems. This data includes physical, chemical, biological, and acoustic measurements, often in real-time or delayed mode.

Information is structured using standardized formats such as NetCDF (CF-compliant) and ODV ASCII, and described using metadata standards like OAI-PMH, DCAT, and schema.org. Persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) are used to ensure traceability and citation. The system supports FAIR principles, enabling findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data.

AOOS integrates data from national and international infrastructures, harmonizing diverse sources through APIs and transformation services. It supports both raw and processed data, with quality control flags and provenance metadata. Sensitive data is handled with appropriate access controls, and licensing constraints are explicitly documented. The information model supports value chains from data acquisition to decision support, ensuring that data is machine-actionable and suitable for scientific, operational, and policy applications.

5.4 Computational viewpoint

The Computational Viewpoint of the AOOS data system defines the functional decomposition of the system into interacting components and services. The system is built around modular services that support data ingestion, transformation, quality control, access, and analytics. These components interact via standardized interfaces such as RESTful APIs and OGC protocols, enabling distributed deployment and integration across platforms.

Figure 3) include:

- Ingestion Services: Collect and ingest data from moorings, floats, buoys, vessels, and observatories.
- Storage Services: Life cycle management of data and products.
- Transformation Services: Extract subsets of large datasets and convert data into standardized formats (e.g., CF-NetCDF, ODV ASCII).
- Data Quality Control Services: Apply automated and manual validation procedures to data and products.
- System monitoring Services: Monitor the health and performance of the services delivered.
- Dissemination Services: Make data available for users. This include publishing discovery metadata and access services for search, access and visualisation. Included in the dissemination is ensuring authority to access and securing integrity between service provider and consumer.
- Analysis Services: Enable processing, modeling, and visualisation of data, including support for machine learning and decision support. This component is external to the AOOS system and relies on existing platforms at institutional, national and regional levels,

These services are loosely coupled, allowing flexibility in deployment and scalability across national and international infrastructures.

Figure 3: Outline of the functional components.

5.5 Engineering viewpoint

The Engineering Viewpoint focuses on the computer infrastructure required to support the distribution and interaction of AOOS data system components. AOOS leverages cloud-native architectures and federated infrastructures to ensure robustness, scalability, and cost-efficiency.

Key engineering elements include:

- Cloud Platforms: Use of Kubernetes-based environments for deploying microservices.
- Storage Systems: File Storage (e.g. Lustre), Object storage (e.g., S3), PostgreSQL databases, and data lakes for managing large volumes of structured and unstructured data.
- Processing Infrastructure: Support for near-data processing via IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, and FaaS models.
- Monitoring & Logging: Tools like Grafana, Prometheus, and Loki for system health and performance tracking.

- Security & Access Control: Implementation of authentication and authorization mechanisms to manage sensitive data and user roles.
- Interoperability Frameworks: Use of standardized APIs and protocols to enable seamless integration across distributed systems.

This infrastructure supports the AOOS goal of delivering reliable, timely, and interoperable ocean data services across diverse user communities.

6 Cost estimate

With the information available so far it is difficult to provide a clear statement on anticipated costs. What is possible is to outline the principles for such an estimate.

It is suggested that the estimate is based on a rental model. This implies that costs are rental cost per e.g., year per unit. This cost includes housing, power, primary support etc. The unit could be Tebabyte for storage, CPU/GPU-hours for processing and GB/s for bandwidth. For storage and processing there are existing rental models available for consultation by e.g. Sigma2 services related to the Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services (NRIS, operated by Sigma2) and MET. These relates to costs for various types of storage (object, parallel etc) as well as processing (HPC, virtual machines, Kubernetes). What isn't available is costs for software as a service etc. In the commercial market there are similar rental models, although the business model is slightly different. In commercial services, storage is often priced low while bandwidth is priced high. For most of the research and governmental services, bandwidth is priced low since there is free capacity while capacity is often maxed out on processing and storage.

The actual cost would require a detailed knowledge of all systems to be implemented, the requirements for research versus operational use (i.e. the need for resilience and duplication) and size of the activity. On premise private or hybrid cloud approaches often out-compete outsourced solutions to industry, but only above a certain threshold size. This implies that smaller actors/activities often benefit from a outsourcing. Outsourcing can be done to a commercial market but also internally between e.g. governmental agencies. The latter has to certain extent been done within the footprint of the Ministry of Climate and Environment.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ADC	Arctic Data Centre
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act (EU)
AOOS	Arctic Ocean Observing System
API	Application Programming Interface
CDSE	Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem
CC-BY-4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License
CF	Climate and Forecast (Conventions for NetCDF)
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CPU/GPU	Central Processing Unit / Graphics Processing Unit
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DP	Data Peak (NIRD)
DL	Data Lake (NIRD)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FFI	Norwegian Defence Research Establishment
GB/s	Gigabytes per second
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit

GTS	Global Telecommunication System (WMO)
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IARPC	Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee
IMR	Institute of Marine Research
I/O	Input/Output
K8s	Kubernetes
LoVe Ocean	Lofoten–Vesterålen Ocean Observatory
MET	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
METSIS	MET Scientific Information System
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration (US)
NERSC	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NIRD	National Infrastructure for Research Data
NIVA	Norwegian Institute for Water Research
NLOD	Norwegian Licence for Open Government Data
NMDC	Norwegian Marine Data Centre
NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute
NRIS	Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services
ODV ASCII	Ocean Data View ASCII Format
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
PaaS	Platform as a Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
RM-ODP	Reference Model of Open Distributed Processing
S3	Simple Storage Service (object storage)
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System
SoP	State of Polarization (sensing)
SPN	Space Norway

STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
SaaS	Software as a Service
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology (repository principles)
UIT (UiT)	The Arctic University of Norway
VM	Virtual Machine
WekEO	Copernicus Harmonised Data Access Platform
WIS / WIS 2.0	WMO Information System (versions 1 and 2)
WMO	World Meteorological Organization